

Zootopia - Verbal Adaptation 1

Zootopia is a vibrant city where savage animals and pets coexist in harmony and live in peace.

There is a play in a school. Judy, a young rabbit girl, is the star of the school play.

In the play, a tiger boy shouts: "Die, rabbit!" and pretends to attack Judy. She dramatically responds, "Nooo! I am dying! I am dying sooooo much!" She falls to the ground in an exaggerated manner while she says: "Blood! Blood! Blood!".

Her parents, watching from the audience, feel embarrassed by her exaggerated performance.

Judy speaks to the audience and introduces the main theme of the play: "There are two kinds of animals: savage animals and cute pets like me."

A character representing "Evolution" steps in and says to the tiger and the rabbit: "Hi, I am Evolution. Now you two can live in peace."

The rabbit continues her speech: "Nowadays, savage animals and pets live together, and we can be whatever we want." Various characters step forward and dream aloud: "I want to be an astronaut!" "I want to work in a bank!" And the little rabbit girl boldly declares:

"I want to be... a police officer!"

The public claps, but her parents look worried.

After the play, Judy and her parents walk through the school festival. They ask their daughter: "Honey, do you really want to be a police officer?"

"Yes," she confidently replies.

Her parents try to reason with her: "Honey, you know that is impossible, right?"

“Why?”

“There are no rabbit cops. No one. Zero.”

The girl looks disappointed, “Really?”

“We are sorry, honey”.

But then she declares, “So, I am going to be the first one!”

Her parents suggest: “And... don’t you prefer to work in the farm? With us? And with your three hundred siblings...?” But Judy is not there, she is gone. “Judy? Where... Where is she?”

Judy sees a big fox bullying her friends. “Give me those tickets!” He demands and takes the tickets. The young rabbit steps forward, trying to defend her friends. “Stop! Give those tickets back to my friends!” she shouts.

The bully mocks her, “Oh, no! It’s the super rabbit cop! I’m so scared!” and pushes her. She falls and her eyes fill with tears. He laughs cruelly. “Cry, stupid rabbit. Cry.” But she doesn’t back down. In a sudden turn, she kicks the bully in the head.

But he attacks her, scratching her face.

The fox leaves and laughs, “Stupid rabbit. She never knows when to give up.”

Her friends, concerned, ask Judy, “Are you okay?”. She answers by giving them back the tickets. “Here are your tickets”. Her friends, surprised, cheer her on. “Wow!” “You are the best, Judy!” “That fox is just an idiot.”

Judy, still hurt, quietly says, “No, he is right...”

Judy stands and claims: “I never know when to give up!”

To be continued...